

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

D3.1 – Cross-Chart of ORRI Services

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D3.1.Cross-chart of ORRI Services

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ORRI SERVICES AT A GLANCE

Open Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) is a process that considers the broader impacts of research and innovation, marking a paradigm shift in their conduct. Its goal is to ensure that the positive societal and economic benefits of research and innovation are fully realized, while minimizing unintended negative impacts. However, implementing ORRI often encounters significant challenges and barriers. Achieving the necessary shift in research and innovation systems is difficult, particularly when ORRI goals and [principles](#) appear to conflict with objectives deemed of higher value, importance, or urgency. Consequently, numerous resources and tools for ORRI have been developed over the past decade.

In order to contribute to achieving REINFORCING's main goal, i.e. to provide meaningful support, services, and resources to as many ORRI enablers as possible to enhance ORRI mainstreaming, we have designed and deployed the [digital ORRI Platform](#) as a one-stop source (OSS) for resources and support services for ERA institutions and territories. The OSS provides a broad range of knowledge and expertise to support organizations and territories on their ORRI journey.

This Deliverable (D3.1) is a cross-chart of **support services**, i.e., an overview of what the REINFORCING project provides for its grantees and the ORRI community at large.

D3.1. Cross-chart of ORRI Services

The data collected in this deliverable provides inputs to *T5.1 Impact Assessment of Addressed Gaps* and to assess the efficacy of the OSS raising awareness activities in *T6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan*, and again in M48 (D3.1). It thus serves as an instrument to document usage across the ERA to make adjustments, if necessary, in the next project period.

The cross-chart below provides an overview of the types of service provided and related descriptive statistics of usage. We also supply additional information through features such as the main target group, the mode as well as the status of delivery.

Service types comprise:

- **Community Building** for ORRI practitioners (experts, grantees) in Europe and beyond: Platform, Helpdesk, Grants, ORRI Map, Global Network, Global Forum.
- Useful **Resources** to support the design of ORRI practices with concrete **Tools** and **Pathways** for implementing ORRI.
- **Training** and **Mentoring** for **building the capacity** on ORRI and institutionalize the ORRI approach.

Service features relate to:

- Main target groups
 - **ORRI Community** (at large)
 - **ORRI Practitioners** (experts, grantees)
- Mode of delivery
 - **Digital** (online)
 - **Physical** (in-person)
- Status of delivery (per August 2025)
 - **Designed** (design available)
 - **Delivered** (in full operation)

CROSS-CHART OF ORRI SERVICES

	Service (plus features)	
Community-Building	<p>Platform The one-stop source to support ORRI practitioners with easily accessible knowledge and expertise.</p> <p>Digital Community Delivered</p> <p>Access statistics: - Number of visits: 55.188 - Average duration of stay: 1 min and 38 seconds</p>	<p>Helpdesk An e-mail-based service for ORRI practitioners (info@reinforcing.eu).</p> <p>Digital Community Delivered</p> <p>Total number of requests: 20-25. Mostly related to Open Calls.</p>
	<p>Grants Provide financial support to European organizations to support their journey towards ORRI.</p> <p>Digital Community Delivered</p> <p>1st ORRI Booster Call Total number of grants: 6 Breakdown of grants awarded by nationality: Spain (1), France (1), Italy (2), Bulgaria (1), Serbia (1) Breakdown by organisation type: Private organisations (6), public organisation (1)</p>	<p>ORRI Map of Ambassadors and Facilitators Helps institutions connect with local experts, matching their need for specific competencies.</p> <p>Digital Community Delivered</p> <p>Total number of Ambassadors and Facilitators: 24. By Country: AT(2), BA(1), BE(2), DE(2), ES(4), IT(5), FI(1), ME(1), NL(1), RO(2), SE(1), SR(2).</p>

D3.1. Cross-chart of ORRI Services

	<p>1st ORRI Incubator Call Total number of grants: 8</p> <p>Breakdown of grants awarded by nationality: Serbia and Bosnia Herzegovina (1), Austria and Albania (1), Romania and Spain (1), Kosovo and North Macedonia (1), Romania (1), Bulgaria (1), Croatia (1), Serbia (1)</p> <p>Breakdown by organisation type: Private organisations (10), public organisations (6)</p> <p>-</p> <p>2nd ORRI Incubator Call Total number of grants: 8</p> <p>Breakdown of grants awarded by nationality: Slovenia and North Macedonia (1), Spain (1) 1 Spain and Portugal (1), Bosnia Herzegovina and Croatia (1), Greece and Spain (1), Slovenia (1), Denmark (1), Hungary (1)</p> <p>Breakdown by organisation type: Private organisations (13), public organisations (5)</p>	
	<p>Global Network Strengthen knowledge and collaboration among ORRI expert practitioners across different sectors in Europe and beyond.</p> <p>Digital Physical Community Delivered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number of members: 22 - By continent: Europe (4), North America (4), South America (3), Africa (3), Asia (5), Australia (3) - Total number of meetings: 5 	<p>Global Forum International forum to explore global perspectives and mainstream responsibility and openness to shape the future of ORRI by sharing good practices.</p> <p>Physical Digital Community Delivered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number of participants: 86 (49 onsite, 37 online) - Total number of practices submitted: 49

D3.1. Cross-chart of ORRI Services

<p>Resources</p>	<p>Tools Concrete tools and best practices for implementing ORRI.</p> <p>Digital Community Delivered</p> <p>REINFORCING platform: 353 (268 visible)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number of Tools: 66 - Total number of Publications: 39 - Total number of Recommendations: 13 - Total number of Success Stories: 150 	<p>Pathways A thematic guide through tools to guide any interested parties in their ORRI journey.</p> <p>Digital Community Designed</p>
<p>Capacity-Building</p>	<p>Trainings Training modules on ORRI to acquire the necessary skillset for implementing ORRI projects.</p> <p>Digital Physical Community Practitioners Delivered</p> <p>CRASH COURSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number: 5 - Number of registrations: 272 - Number of participants: 83 <p>CLINICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number: 3 - Number of registrations: 121 - Number of participants: 30 <p>TRAINING FOR GRANTEES (Balkans and Missions)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of participants: 37 	<p>Mentoring for Grantees Targeted support for newcomers ORRI practitioners in stabilizing the ORRI approach in their institutions.</p> <p>Digital Practitioners Delivered</p> <p>MENTORING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number of mentoring activities activated: 8 (Balkans) - Total number of mentoring activities finalized: 8 (Balkans)